

Nitration and Bromination of 1-Hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole

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In connection with some other work, the information on the position taken by substituents in substitution reaction in 1-hydroxy-1, 2, 3 -benzotriazole was needed. The same is described in this communication. Hydroxybenzotriazole can be easily brominated and nitrated in acetic acid solution. In each case the bromine or the nitro group enters at position 6.

Nitration.—To a solution of 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole (5 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml) was added dropwise fuming nitric acid (3 ml, *d* 1.5). The mixture was heated on a water bath for about an hour. It was cooled and neutralised with sodium carbonate. When the mixture was acidified with HCl (conc.), concentrated, and cooled, a yellow compound (1.5 g.) separated. It was identified as 6-nitro-1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole as the compound alone or mixed with an authentic specimen¹ melted at 198°. (Found: N, 30.97. Calc. for C₆H₄O₃N₄: N, 31.11%)

An attempt to nitrate the above benzotriazole with a mixture of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ caused oxidation of the benzene part of the ring, affording 4,5-dicarboxy-1-hydroxy-1,2,3-triazole.

Bromination.—A solution of bromine (8 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml) was added slowly to a solution of 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole (6.5 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml). The mixture was left overnight and then heated on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled, and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The solution was acidified with HCl (conc.) and concentrated. On cooling, a bromo-1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole separated as colorless crystals (4 g.). It was identified as 6-bromo-1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole as the compound alone or mixed with an authentic specimen² melted at 196°. (Found: Br, 37.14. Calc. for C₆H₄ON₃Br: Br, 37.38%).

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